

DEFECTIVE ANNUAL INCREMENT POLICY AND ITS IMPACT

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Abstract:

Annual Increment is one of the most awaited events in the life of an employee. All members of the job wait for this declaration with equal interest. Males and females equally desire to have a fair increment for their performances. Factors like qualification, achievements, contribution, publication, participation, customer feedback, willingness to take responsibility, team work, etc. are the basis for appraisal system which decides employees' annual increment. The case highlights the defective rationale for deciding increment for employee in an educational institute.

The irrational decision policy demotivates to the extent that employee withdraws herself from active role to passive role and decides to quit.

Key words: Appraisal, Discrimination, Annual Increment, Employee Expectation

Note: The case is intended to be used as basis for classroom discussion rather than to illustrate either effective or ineffective handling of a management situation. The case has been written on the basis of generalized experience.

Defective annual increment policy and its impact

This is a case of one of the leading educational institutes in the field of technical education in Rajkot, Gujarat. With a mission 'to make every student a gentlemen for the nation by an overall personality development of the student through good discipline', institute highlights the importance of discipline in their culture. The institute believes and advocates holistic management practices. It has enjoyed its monopoly in the market in last 10 years, as there is no other institute in that area, geographically as well as in the field of similar technical education field.

The program offered in the institute is of undergraduate level. With a total strength of seventeen regular faculty members including four female faculties in various capacities there are another eleven visiting academic staff too.

Institute has its pay structure according to various grades for teaching as well as non-teaching staff. Generally employees have a stable working day and receive the decided payment for it, but yearly salary increment is something which each and every, big and small employee look for. Monetary part of the increment is important, but more important is the fairness in the entire process and recognition of employee contribution.

Yearly increments are due for and everyone is hoping to get their fair share of due. The appraisal system is of two dimensional; self-appraisal by the candidate itself and then by the management. Management rely on its own judgement of employee's performance and contribution for which they use informal ways of observation.

Mridula, a management faculty in the capacity of senior lecture, was also expecting a good rise in package as it was a fantastic year for her. She had been appreciated for her dedication and command over subjects. Management at

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various point of time accepted her contribution in other services also, be it for Business English Certification examination arrangement or educational presentation for promotional purposes Mridula has been in fore front. Her crisp, well-articulated voice and presentable personality gives inferior complex to many other male faculty members in the institute.

The day arrives and the increments are declared by the management for every individual separately.

Highly enthusiastic, Mridula (real identity kept confidential), gets disheartened when the increment awarded to her were much below than her expectation. Most disappointing is that some of the male employees in same grade were rewarded better than her. She is puzzled, could not understand why such lesser increment is awarded to her in spite of several appreciation for her work in past. In fact she was involved in additional work by the management for seeing her competency in other areas. And, as a matter of working enthusiast she readily took up the additional job. With all these in her mind she approaches Uday, HR manager, with her grievances. Uday asks her written representation. She determined to sort it out, writes to the organization;

To,

The HR Manager,

Subject: *Representation against the discrepancy in awarding increments to similarly placed as the under*

Dear Sir/Madam,

The undersigned humbly requests you to take a perusal of the matter stated above. As will be recalled, the award of increments in a matter related to an employee against a particular post/designation (hence, the pay scale), educational qualifications, and length of services. It came in light that a judicial decision has not been taken by the concerned authorities in awarding the increments to the similarly placed employees as the undersigned.

The qualification of the undersigned exceed far more than the other colleague. The undersigned is a double post graduate and highly qualified in her area of work. Besides, the undersigned has two publications in reputed journals. Secondly, the undersigned is involved in teaching varied subjects as and when assigned by management. Thirdly, the length of the service of the undersigned is more than those employees who have been awarded greater pay scale and consequential benefits.

You will agree that such a discrepancy certainly brings frustration and dissatisfaction to the employee who is being discriminated on such grounds. Under the circumstances, it is requested that the grievance of the undersigned may kindly be forwarded to concerned authorities with suitable strong recommendation from your side.

Sincerely,

Mridula

Sr. Lecturer

Mridula waited for the response from the management, as it was told to her that management will look into the matter and revert. But nothing is communicated in a period of 15days.

The Aftermath:

As Mridula, did not hear any response for 15 days from HR Manager, so she sends a gentle reminder, in response she gets a very illogical answer (verbally) from Uday saying “Mridula, he (other male faculty who got a better increment) has to run a family with this salary, in your (Mridula) case things are different.”

Owing to this unsatisfactory response from HR Manager about her pay and things were rumbling in her head, Mridula was unable to focus on job. She detached herself from active participation in multiple activities. But nothing came to her console so she decided to directly speak to the senior management, the main authority for decision about pay.

She mentioned all her concerns and upsets that the entire episode was not very motivating. She felt like there is no point working that hard if she is not getting rewarded for it.

Later on, she decided to take another assignment in some other organization and applied for another job. As the luck favoured, she gets a nice opportunity, and was about to shift, but her gut feeling said not to give up at that moment, otherwise it will give a wrong message. She had a strong feeling that ‘I am not being treated right’. Moreover, she wanted to leave the organization for her own reason, not because of any provocation.

Employee Expectation from Management:

- 1) A prompt response from management within stipulated time period is expected in the case. A timely action and an honest effort from management could dilute the complexity of the situation.
- 2) Secondly, the reply (after gentle reminder) from HR Manager, clearly states a case of gender discrimination, which is un-ethical as per equal policy act. Management should not go with popular notion of the society that males run the family and females do not.
Also, management should encourage high performance irrespective of gender. This is mandatory to establish a positive and healthy work environment.
- 3) Excellence can be achieved only when an employee put her whole hearted effort into her work. Undoubtedly, that level of motivation depends upon certain factors, such as;
 - Equal pay policy
 - Award for performance
 - No sex discrimination, etc.

Management could have adopted such practices to address the issue and also for its long run.

Concluding Point

After few more days, Mridula receives a mail from HR stating management is willing to hold a discussion on her points on a desirable date. Management clarifies their stand that organization was very much willing to treat every employee fairly. The regular practices thus far have been compensating male employee more than a female counterpart, since it is perceived that the responsibilities to run a family lies mainly on male member of the society, which is not true in today's scenario. Management appreciated Mridula for showing the nerve to raise such difficult issue with the management and not going on back-foot. Management promised to revamp their management practices.